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The Effect of Teacher Competence on Learning Implementation in Project Based Blended Learning Model

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of teacher competence on learning implementation in project-based blended learning. This study uses quantitative research methods with experimental research types. The research subjects were 40 teachers, 20 certified teachers and 20 non-certified teachers. Data collection techniques used questionnaires and observations to review teacher competence. Data analysis used homogeneity test, normality test and hypothesis testing. Based on the research results, the research data is homogeneous and statistically normally distributed. And the results of hypothesis testing show that there is an influence of teacher competence on the implementation of learning in project-based blended learning statistically. As for further research, it can examine and research related to the influence of the teacher's educational background in other fields of education, both from early school to college. Teacher competence is very necessary because the factors that influence the achievement of learning objectives based on education, teaching experience and length of teaching, are the key to success in achieving educational goals. So, it is required for a teacher to have professional competence to support the quality of education, especially in special education

Keywords: Teacher Competence, Project-Based Learning, Certified, Learning

1. Introduction

In order to meet the ever-evolving demands of the times, qualified teachers will always work to develop their professional and pedagogical competences, including the capacity to plan, carry out, and assess learning. A teacher ought to plan as much as possible. These plans cover learning objectives, resources, activities, techniques, and assessment of learning (Riadi, 2017). According to Sagala, there are ten fundamental skills that a teacher must possess. These skills include: mastery of the material being taught; management of teaching and learning programs; management of classes; proficiency with media and learning resources; mastery of educational foundations; management of teaching and learning interactions; assessment of students' learning outcomes for teaching purposes; recognition of the roles and programs of guidance and counseling services; recognition and organization of school administration; and comprehension of teaching and learning (Hasanah et al., 2024).

In the context of formal education in schools, instructors play a critical role in raising educational standards. Educators are at the center of putting education into practice. Stated differently, educators hold the greatest sway over the development of high-quality learning procedures and results. Qualified teachers are essential to the education and teaching process; therefore, in addition to being experts in their fields and in their pedagogies, teachers also need to comprehend the fundamentals of education (Sopian, 2016). Teachers are viewed as people who have the ability to positively impact the community because they are perceived as natural leaders who can offer guidance on a range of issues (Bourn, 2016). Teachers can be considered qualified if they can meet the following nine criteria, according to Gage & Berliner: they should be able to help students maximize their learning outcomes; they should genuinely dedicate their time to understanding participants in a humane and authentic way; they should be able to manage the learning process effectively; they should also have a sense of humor; they should be able to make students feel comfortable learning; they should be enthusiastic or have a positive attitude in teaching; they should be fair to each individual student; and they should be able to encourage students to take ownership of their education (Hermayawati, 2018).

Thus, without the assistance of qualified and experienced teachers, no development efforts devoted to education will be very successful. Thus, there is a demand for educators who are highly qualified, competent, and committed to doing their jobs well. The accomplishment of learning objectives based on education, experience, and time of instruction is influenced by teacher competence. The secret to accomplishing educational objectives is the proficiency of teachers. Because of this, one could say that teachers are professionals. As such, they need to be competent in all areas of teaching, management, guidance, motivation, and interaction with the outside world in order to fulfill their responsibility to help students reach their full potential and develop their character (Kadri et al., 2022). Professional competence is the ability to grasp the concepts, structure, vocabulary, and scientific way of thinking that underpin the disciplines that are taught (Siswanto & Supeno, 2022). The information, abilities, attitudes, and values required to be a competent and successful teacher are all included in the idea of teacher professional competence. A teacher must be able to guide pupils to reach standards by having a broad and deep mastery of the content they are teaching. This is known as professional competence (Ulfa et al., 2024).

In line with the above objectives, the Regulation of the Director General of Teachers and Education Personnel (Perdirjen GTK) Number 4141/B/HK.06/1003 concerning Guidelines for Continuous Competency Development for Teachers in article 2 states that teachers need to develop competencies as an effort to fulfill teacher competencies with job standards and/or career development plans. This situation is no exception for teachers who provide services for children with special needs or also called special mentor teachers. Learning services for children with special needs should be provided in accordance with the range of inadequacies they possess. Teachers who have obtained sufficient education and training in line with the range of children's deficits will offer high-quality services. The community, the government, parents, and educational institutions in particular share responsibility for providing special education services to children (Anidar, 2016). In order to maximize potential and uphold human dignity, educational services for children with exceptional needs are fundamentally humanitarian endeavors, according to humanistic psychology (Fitrianingrum et al., 2023). In inclusive schools, the teacher's role is crucial since it marks a turning point in the learning process and calls for the ability to integrate a diverse curriculum (Abdah, 2019). Given the existing circumstances, it is appropriate for educators, parents, and the general public to be aware of children with special needs. This is to ensure that no one believes that kids with special needs are weak people who don't need access to school (Simamora et al., 2022).

Learning services for children with special needs should be provided in accordance with the range of inadequacies they possess. Teachers that have gotten sufficient education and training in line with the range of deficits exhibited by the children will provide quality services. Children who significantly (that is, differently from other children their age) encounter physical, mental-intellectual, social, emotional, or anomalies during their growth or development and hence need special education services are considered special needs children (Azmi & Nurmaya, 2020). Children who, because of their diseases or anomalies, require special services or therapy in order to develop to their full potential are considered to have special needs (Rezieka et al., 2021). Additionally, there are distinctions or inadequacies in significant domains for children with special needs. They struggle on a psychological, physical, and social level to reach their needs, desires, and full potential. Therefore, it requires extra attention in this instance in all educational and interpersonal activities (Iswati & Rohaningsih, 2021). Like other typical children of the same

age, children with special needs can also get education that is adapted to meet their requirements. Children with special needs can have mental, emotional, and other issues that arise from within them in addition to physical difficulties. As a result, participatory education arranges instruction for both typical students and kids with special needs based only on their shared qualities (Habibah et al., 2024).

Special education programs, inclusive schools, therapy, and other forms of special supervision can all be used to provide educational assistance for children with special needs. Teachers with particular expertise are needed for all of these programs. It is expected of teachers with training in inclusion and special education that they possess a greater understanding of successful learning practices for kids with special needs. Teaching in inclusive classrooms firsthand can provide educators real-world understanding of the difficulties and achievements involved in planning, carrying out, and assessing instruction for children with diverse needs.

Special mentor teachers are responsible for planning, implementing and evaluating learning. Special mentor teachers provide individualized support to children with special needs by providing guidance, monitoring and coaching. They help identify the most effective learning strategies according to each student's specific needs. To support the implementation of inclusive education, support is needed from specialized experts in the field of education for children with special needs, namely the role of special mentor teachers. Special mentor teachers play a role in every teaching process for students who have limitations and differences in psychological and physical aspects so that children with special needs can carry out learning with services to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of achieving the learning objectives to be achieved (Ansari et al., 2021). Therefore, in addition to lecturing or dictating without taking into account the differences in students' abilities, talents, and interests, teachers also have a responsibility to maximize school services for students with special needs (Yusuf, 2022). In order to provide their pupils with effective learning strategies throughout the learning process, specialized guidance teachers working with children can create and choose learning materials and learning tactics that are appropriate for the diverse backgrounds of their students (Rasyada et al., 2022).

Teachers that practice inclusive education must encourage collaboration amongst students with varying needs when conducting lessons. This involves establishing a setting that encourages inclusive and constructive interactions. Throughout the teaching process, educators need to be ready to quickly modify their lesson plans in response to the demands and responses of their students. Adaptability is essential when discussing inclusiveness. Instructors have a part to play in regulating the environment that surrounds the learning process throughout teaching and learning activities (Yestiani & Zahwa, 2020). It's possible to compare it to the teacher operating the controls and guiding the ship toward a secure and comfortable destination. A teacher needs to be able to establish a welcoming and cozy learning environment in the classroom. In order to provide pupils with a secure, orderly, and disciplined learning environment while they are studying, teachers serve as classroom managers (Sulistiani & Nugraheni, 2023).

To make sure that children with special needs receive the assistance they require throughout their education, special needs education teachers must keep a close eye on their students' participation and development. Thus, educators need to be very careful while selecting the best learning model or one that can effectively support the learning process. Using a project-based blended learning strategy is one of them. It is a hybrid learning paradigm that combines blended learning with project-based learning. It employs both online and offline learning environments while implementing the Merdeka Curriculum, which is currently being implemented in Indonesia. Online learning is predicted to keep expanding and possibly overtake traditional classroom instruction at some point in the future (Schleicher, 2020), (Dhawan, 2020), (Trinova et al., 2022). Of course, the Merdeka Curriculum is still in use since it is thought to hold the key to resolving Indonesia's educational crisis. When compared to other curricula, the Merdeka Curriculum stands out due to its emphasis on using the Project Based Learning learning model, which is learner-centered and capable of fostering students' independence.

The Merdeka curriculum essentially incorporates the effects of every social change that has occurred at this point (Indarta et al., 2022). The Merdeka Curriculum is built with students' growth and attainment levels in mind. This ensures that the curriculum meets students' needs precisely and promotes engaging and joyful learning (Dewi, 2022). This makes a learning model characterized by student centered can be the right choice as a form of

implementing the Merdeka Curriculum. There are quite a variety of learner-oriented learning models, such as discussion methods, contextual methods, problem-based learning models, project-based learning models, and so on. On the other hand, the application of technology in learning also needs to be involved so that learning can be done anywhere and anytime, so that learning becomes more meaningful and can train students' independence. Technology integration is possible through the blended learning approach, which makes use of a number of currently expanding platform services. Additionally, project-based learning, blended learning, and their combination—that is, project-based blended learning in the early childhood education context—will be covered in this section. As a result, special assistant instructors need to be highly qualified and capable of integrating project-based blended learning into their lesson plans.

According to earlier studies, teacher performance is significantly impacted by teacher competency (Rohman, 2020). The results of other studies show that teachers' pedagogical competence has a significant effect on the quality of learning (Rosyada et al., 2021). The results of other studies show that teacher competence has a significant effect on learning success (Sirait, 2021). The results of other studies state that there is a significant influence between the influence of educator competence and the quality of educators (Marlina et al., 2022). The results of other studies show that there is an effect of teacher competence on the understanding of subject matter (Maulidya & Ulfah, 2023). Based on some of the research results above, it can be explained that the competence of educators is very influential in the quality of learning, exploring subject matter, determining the quality of teachers, which at its main point improves the implementation of learning.

Based on the explanation above, the purpose of this study is the effect of teacher competence on learning implementation in project-based blended learning.

2. Method

The research method used in this research is quantitative method with experimental research type. This research uses a quantitative approach with experimental research. The experimental research carried out is a quasi experiment or quasi experimental. The quasi experiment tests whether there is a causal relationship between the independent and dependent variables (Loewen & Plonsky, 2016). Experimental research aims to establish cause-and-effect relationships by testing an idea, practice, or procedure to determine how much the independent variable affects the outcome or dependent variable (Akbar et al., 2023).

In this study, the research subjects were all inclusive education teachers with a total of 40 teachers. The focus of this study included special education teachers who assist students with special needs, the qualifications needed and training received by special education teachers to optimize their role in inclusive schools, and effective teaching methods and strategies used by special education teachers in teaching students with special needs in inclusive schools. In this study, there were 20 teachers with a special education background and 20 teachers who did not come from special education. Data analysis techniques for teacher competence used questionnaires and observation of the implementation of special assistance teachers. Data analysis used homogeneity test, normality test and hypothesis testing.

3. Results

Analysis of homogeneity test on the number of research subjects as many as 20 certified teachers and 20 non-certified teachers, then the homogeneity test uses Levene Statistic.

Table 1: Homogeneity Test Results

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances^a		
	F	Sig.
Learning Implementation	.160	.692

Table 1 shows homogeneity for learning implementation in both special education and non-special education, in the Levene Statistic test, the significance is $0.692 > 0.05$, which means that the data is statistically homogeneous..

Normality test analysis on the number of research subjects as many as 20 certified teachers and 20 non-certified teachers, the homogeneity test uses Kolmogorov-Smimov and Shapiro Wilk.

Table 2: Normality Test Results

Tests of Normality							
	Learning_Model	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Learning Implementation	Non-Special Education	.147	20	.200*	.936	20	.199
	Special Education	.173	20	.119	.928	20	.140

Table 2 shows normality for learning implementation in both special education and non-special education in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests. The use of Shapiro-Wilk was chosen because the sample was less than 100 people. The significance of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test on learning implementation for non-special education teachers is $0.200 > 0.05$, which means the data is normal, special education teachers are $0.119 > 0.05$, which means the data is normal. Shapiro-Wilk test, on non-special education teacher learning planning $0.199 > 0.05$, which means normal data, special education teachers $0.140 > 0.05$, which means normal data.

Hypothesis test analysis on the number of research subjects as many as 20 certified teachers and 20 non-certified teachers, the homogeneity test uses the Univariate Analysis of Variance test.

Table 3: Hypothesis Test Results

Dependent Variable: Implementation

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1149.875 ^a	4	287.469	609.782	.000
Intercept	201081.802	1	201081.802	426537.155	.000
Competence	137.254	1	137.254	291.145	.000
Error	16.500	35	.471		
Total	220947.000	40			
Corrected Total	1166.375	39			

Based on table 3, Tests of Between-Subjects Effects for the effect of educational background on the learning implementation in project-based blended learning for special supervising teachers in inclusive schools, it is known that Sig. count 0.000. The result of this Sig. count is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$).

In the Results section, summarize the collected data and the analysis performed on those data relevant to the discourse that is to follow. Report the data in sufficient detail to justify your conclusions. Mention all relevant results, including those that run counter to expectation; be sure to include small effect sizes (or statistically nonsignificant findings) when theory predicts large (or statistically significant) ones. Do not hide uncomfortable results by omission. Do not include individual scores or raw data with the exception, for example, of single-case designs or illustrative examples. In the spirit of data sharing (encouraged by APA and other professional associations and sometimes required by funding agencies), raw data, including study characteristics and individual effect sizes used in a meta-analysis, can be made available on supplemental online archives.

4. Discussion

The ability of special mentor teachers to execute learning in inclusive schools is significantly influenced by their level of competence. Robust proficiencies encompass an in-depth comprehension of educational philosophy, particular knowledge of the needs of students with special needs, and effective teaching approaches. Highly competent educators are able to create and carry out efficient lesson plans that guarantee every student receives the guidance and assistance they require to learn as much as possible (Asyafah, 2019). For any teacher to be effective, they must first ensure that they possess self-competence, which includes a wide range of knowledge and insights, abilities, as well as a more motivated attitude and dedication to achieving effective learning management.

Secondly, to bolster the role of educators as catalysts for change in education that is, as change agents who are open to new ideas and quick to adapt to evolving knowledge for ongoing professional growth. Third, to prepare teachers to be developers with a broad perspective, a strong vision for education, and the ability to face and effect transformation in the face of evolving times (Wahyuni & Haryanti, 2024). Teacher competence is the foundation of education. Competent teachers are the key to improving the quality of education and promoting effective learning. Learners' skills and abilities are a direct result of the quality of teacher competence in the school environment (Tahajudin et al., 2023).

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects have a known Sig. count of 0.000 for the influence of competence on a teacher's capacity to apply learning. Given that the Sig. count result is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). We can conclude that certified teachers apply knowledge more effectively than non-certified ones.

Strong interpersonal skills are another aspect of good competence that helps teachers interact with peers, parents, and students in an effective manner. Building a welcoming and inclusive learning environment requires competent instructors to establish strong, enduring relationships with their pupils. The capacity for communication is a crucial component of learning since it allows students to share information with teachers and other students as well as express their opinions (Marfuah, 2017). One way that communication skills benefit students during the learning process is that they make it easier for them to comprehend the messages and information that teachers convey to them through subject matter. Additionally, kids who possess strong communication skills are able to respond to questions, articulate their thoughts and opinions, and ask brave questions when they are having trouble grasping a concept (Fitriah et al., 2020). Along with working with parents and other professionals to assist students' development, effective communication skills are also important for understanding and meeting the unique needs of each student (Perdana et al., 2023).

Additionally, in the context of special education, proficiency with educational technology is becoming more and more crucial. Technology-savvy educators can employ a variety of digital tools to enhance learning, produce more interesting materials, and give students alternative ways to access information. By leveraging technology effectively, learning obstacles can be removed and children with special needs can be taught in a manner that best meets their needs. Technology integration in the classroom, according to Bower and Sturman, can boost more adaptive learning and raise student engagement (Tulak et al., 2024).

In general, special mentor teachers may provide efficient and adaptable instruction in inclusive schools when they possess good abilities. Positivity toward students and parents, technology assistance for learning, and the creation and implementation of adaptive teaching practices are all possible for instructors who possess strong competences. This raises the standard of instruction while guaranteeing that each student has an equal opportunity to grow and realize their full potential.

5. Conclusion

There is an effect of educational competence on the implementation of learning in project-based blended learning for special mentor teachers in inclusive schools as indicated by the Sig. value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that teachers with special education are better at implementing learning than non-special education teachers. Especially for special assistant teachers who have experience in the field of inclusive education or education in special schools, teacher competence has a significant role in making learning implementation for students with special needs. The learning process becomes better because it has been managed by special assistant teachers with professional competence. Supported by project-based blended learning as a platform that adapts to the learning process, which offers many benefits to improve teaching standards. Thus, the findings of this study offer strong empirical evidence and appropriate information according to the research needs. This research can be understood that the information presented is still categorized as not broad, because it only examines special mentor teachers for children with special needs and the scope of inclusive education or special education only. It is hoped that further research can examine and examine the influence of teacher competence in other fields of education, both from elementary schools to universities. Regarding competent teachers in private and public educational institutions.

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